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Use of Graph Technology to Identify Criminal Activity Using Call Data Record

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Abstract :

Crime is a global issue and the first move must be to control it. For a nation to experience healthy, long-term growth, it is essential. We are well aware of the challenges in identifying the criminal domains in the digital world that are constantly influenced by their misdeeds. To stay up with crimes, offenders, and their tactics, police forces across the globe pace themselves continually. The difficulty of sifting through a large amount of data on crimes and criminals has grown significantly for the police department labor force. There is a need for a system that can categorize and thoroughly investigate. Using various strategies and concepts, police personnel can identify and stop crimes in society.

In this study, we propose a novel model for investigating how graph technologies might be used to analyze Call Detail Records (CDR) in order to detect potential offenders. We are charged with the arduous task of using an unsupervised data analysis approach without including any prior knowledge about the application context in the model, automatically producing appropriate information from available data. The outcomes of graph data mining are used to create profiling data, identify anomalies, and analyze user behavior.

Keywords : Crime, call data record, graph db, neo4j, cypher, data mining.

1. Introduction :

Call detail records are extremely extensive and include information like the calling party's (A-party) and the called party's phone numbers. The record may also include facts about the exchange that handled the call, as well as the names, addresses, and identification numbers of both participants. Other information, such as billing details for each party on a specific conversation, may be included in a call detail record. Information regarding calls made from one phone number to another is recorded in call detail records. This can contain information like the date, time, and length of a call, as well as more complicated information like how long the discussion lasted. For tracking the demographics and geographic movements of the population in the past, population censuses were often utilized. A better choice in this respect would be CDRs given the short-term and daily mobility that has led to the use of more flexible approaches like indirect databases and other registries. One of their key benefits is that they may be used to track huge and diverse groups of people and provide a statistically accurate depiction of the distribution of individuals in a region. The information that CDRs contain "automatically" refreshes over time because they alter in response to changes in user behavior. The enormous volume of CDRs that telecom operators regularly collect allows for the extraction of new data at minimal additional expense and the creation of useful datasets. Analysis of CDR data has a wide range of applications, including network monitoring, service adaption (such as customer billing and network planning), and analyzing a region's economic condition. In many criminal investigations, it is common practice to obtain data from cell phones. While it is not expected that cell phone records will identify the source of an offense or provide any new information about the crime itself, some investigators are particularly interested in the metadata

contained within a phone call. In this article, we'll explore how graph technology can be used to analyze and interpret metadata obtained by criminal investigators investigating mobile communication networks.

A. Call data record - The content of a telecommunication transaction is not included in a call detail record, but it does contain data fields that characterize a particular instance of that transaction. For the sake of simplicity, let's assume that a call data record detailing a specific phone call has the phone numbers of the caller and the recipient, as well as the start and end times of the conversation. Modern call detail records really contain much more information, including qualities like disposition or call outcomes like whether an inbound call succeeded or failed. CDR provides the information about which telephone numbers were called from a given phone, where the calls were made from, how long it took, etc.

B. Neo4j - The technology selected to represent graph databases is Neo4j, it's an open source. Production of it has lasted for more than five years. It is rapidly rising to the top of the list of graph database systems. Neo4j is "an integrated, disk-based, fully atomic Java persistence engine that holds data arranged in graphs instead of tables", according to the Neo4j website. Multiple billion nodes may fit on a single system, according to the creators, who also say that the API is simple to use and that it provides fast traversals. Neo4j uses Lucene 3 from Apache for indexing and search. High performance is the focus of Lucene, a Java-based text search engine.

2. Description of the Problem :

CDRs are crucial to all mobile phone providers. These records are essential since they contain all the information about every phone conversation. For example, each of these records contains information of the caller, the person being called, the duration of the call, and so on. Because of the large amount of data and the fact that it is kept in native format & analyzing such data is extremely complex and challenging.

A. Running example - Kisan Vikas Kalyan Sansthan (KVKS) - Fake vacancy case, handed over to me by the crime branch Police in Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh for the analysis /study cum research purpose is illustrated here in the following manner:

This case is of three individuals A1, A2, and A3, trio individuals are from Gwalior, Morena (Madhya Pradesh) and Chhattisgarh. Trio individuals had the malicious intention of forging/looting innocents citizens for that the individuals random set out an advertisement in the newspaper with regards to offering a job in KVKS. Innocent citizens got lured and fall into the trap with respect to taking advertisements offered by A1 and A2 via the newspaper. After that, both the individuals A1 and A2 trapped/lured the targeted innocents and asked them for a sum of amount ₹500 for General and OBC, ₹250 for SC and ST candidates on Account no. BOI0E137197131588666, when the people actually reach out for the job to the mentioned organization with advertisement and for document verification, they found, it was fake, they were trapped and cheated.

During 2013 January, Mr. A1, A2, and A3, trapped 3000 people and looted 6800000 lakh rupees approx. The particular case was discovered by the Bilaspur Police when the FIR got registered by n no. of people. As both accused were using the mobile number for calling each other, their call data records show their present address. The case history was shared for analysis parsley.

3. Building Model :

The data phone providers supply to law enforcement is very tabular. Trying to discover unique calls and their associations in statistical data is quite difficult. As a result, we will create a graph using the phone call data. This graph will demonstrate how phone calls link the phone numbers. We may infer a network with a list of telephone calls. A single phone call links four entities: two phone users, a location (the cell site adjacent to which the caller was when he began the call), date, time & duration of the call.

Fig. 1 : Phone call illustration using Graph model

4. Data Analysis :

A. Call record analysis:

In this section, we'll examine the call histories in an effort to locate the culprit who placed the call. In our case there is group of three people who have involved in this case, two of them keep changing their location while executing the whole incident. We began the study by using the hotline number that these individuals had provided as a starting point.

```

match (m:MakeCall)-[c:CALLED]->(r:RecieveCall)
with m,r,count(c) as count, sum(c.duration) as duration where duration >0
return m.calling_party_A, r.calling_party_B, count as total_calls, duration order by total_calls desc

```

calling_party_A	calling_party_B	total_calls	duration
'918121E+11'	'903955300'	135	30973
'918121E+11'	'91933033001'	10	408
'918121E+11'	'91830951666'	7	390
'918121E+11'	'91933597216'	7	441
'918121E+11'	'91933097216'	7	358
'918121E+11'	'903955300'	6	16474

Image 3 : Represent cypher result in tabular form

Image 3 shows how writing some off-line code led to the solution of such a large CDR using cypher query. In the above image, output are in tabular form whom which we have converted into graph.

Image 4 : Represents the result in graph form

Police officers typically ask phone operators about the calls that occur most often and least rarely. Due to the large amount and complexity of the data, phone operator took time to respond to such a question. We have therefore developed a query of cypher to respond to the query that a police officer might pose. One of the cypher queries we developed is the following:

Image 5 : Representing the maximum called no.

B. Visual analysis of network:

Image 6 : Represent the connection between 3 criminals

The output of running the query is shown in the image 6. We were unable to comprehend the network of our three criminals- A1, A2, and A3 from the graph shown in image 3. However, such a graph is difficult to read because it is fairly dense. This is so that it can represent the three suspects and the individuals they know, which are represented by its 300 nodes and 422 relationships. We can choose one of the criminal to highlight his relationships in order to streamline the graph. We presume that the policeman recognized a few names from the list of names that are associated with the chosen suspect. There are three criminals and the acquaintances of each.

5. Result :

The 33 suspects and the individuals they know are represented by 34 nodes and 150 relationships. When we choose a suspect, his connections will be highlighted. We're going to assume that, as police investigators, you recognise a few names that have already come up in earlier investigations. Although they are not directly connected to the crime we are looking into, these individuals are in touch with someone who is. We may explore that connection visually. The analysis of the calls show that A1, A2, and A3 are connected to one another. They used to communicate with one another via phone conversations and would frequently switch numbers (remember when it was possible to get an unlimited number of SIM cards without providing proof of address back in 2014?). They are a small region within the bigger graph. The initial suspect with the highest probability of becoming a criminal is A1.

6. Conclusion :

Our goal in this research study is to create a system that accepts cellular phone numbers as input and extracts the matching CDRs, producing many databases containing CDRs. After that, it analyses these databases and discovers numerous connections between different suspects (mobile numbers), producing the results of its study as output. This conclusion includes suspect data (location, date, time, etc.). The IT crime cell may move on all of them immediately with a proper analysis of the CDRs of the various suspects.

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